

Whitepaper indicators for material selection used for microfluidic devices

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Introduction

Microfluidics devices can not only pump liquids in channels but can also agitate liquids and implement sensing functions through the implementation of semiconductors. In the case of MPS (microphysiological systems), the device should fit various functions for the user requirements, such as culture and observation of retained cells, temporary introduction of drugs, and even sterilisation prior to use. Such microfluidics devices must, for example, have high transparency during observation, be easily processed depending on the fineness of the flow path, be made of various materials, but should withstand high temperatures and high humidity when used for autoclave sterilisation, etc., in the Context of Use of the device. The materials need to be selected according to the requirements corresponding to the Context of Use of the device.

Requirements for materials are defined for individual processes implemented within the device in order to realise the Context of Use for the device as a whole or with cells, tissues, etc., retained. For example, the material is required to have high transparency for processes requiring microscopic observation, and the material is required to have low autofluorescence when fluorescence microscopy is required. In other cases, when investigating the effects of drugs, it is difficult to select the appropriate material, as the effects of drugs cannot be correctly evaluated unless their adsorption, sorption, etc., are low. The transparency, autofluorescence and drug sorption are considered to be indicators for evaluating materials. However, there is no international consensus on which indicators should be used to decide the requirements for each process of microfluidics devices and how these indicators should be measured and evaluated. This has made it difficult to select appropriate materials when designing and developing microfluidics devices and determine whether users can use them in MPS for their intended applications. This is a challenge in developing and using microfluidic devices and MPS under international cooperation.

This document therefore provides microfluidics device developers with the minimum necessary indicators and evaluation methods for selecting materials according to the overall device Context of Use and internal process requirements of microfluidics devices, such as ease of processing, low fluorescence, high impact strength, transparency, sorption, sorption, oxygen permeability, sterilisation resistance, etc. their evaluation methods.

Definitions

processability

relative ease of processing plastics and resins for moulding into microfluidic devices

Note1 to entry: The processability for rubber was defined in ISO 1382:2020, 3.390.

[SOURCE: ISO 1382:2020, 3.390 modified]

processing accuracy

deviations from design dimensions when resin is processed using injection shaping, cutting or other technologies

autofluorescence

fluorescence (3.1.58) exhibited by virtue of the inherent properties of an object (3.1.104)

[SOURCE: ISO 10934:2020, 3.1.58.1]

impact strength

ability of a material to resist shock loading

[SOURCE: ISO 16525-6:2014, 3.1]

total luminous transmittance

ratio of the transmitted luminous flux to the incident luminous flux when a parallel beam of light passes through a specimen

[SOURCE: ISO 13468-1:2019, 3.2]

plastic transparency

inherent total luminous transmittance of plastic materials

oxygen flux

net volume of oxygen gas passing through a unit area of sample plastic material per unit time under specified conditions, including temperature, sample thickness and partial pressures of oxygen on both sides of the sample

[SOURCE: ISO 18369-1:2017, 3.1.6.9, modified]

oxygen permeability

oxygen flux, under specified conditions through material of unit thickness when subjected to unit pressure difference

[SOURCE: ISO 18369-1:2017, 3.1.6.8, modified]

drug adsorption

physical process in which the molecules of drug to be analysed adhere to the surface of material

[SOURCE: ISO 7183:2007(en), 3.3, modified]

II. Property index of materials used for microfluidics

a. Basic approach to material selection

Materials such as PP and COP are usually used for microfluidic devices and selected according to the properties of the respective material. For example, materials with high transparency and low autofluorescence are preferred for optical measurements.

Microfluidic devices are used for a variety of applications, such as maintaining cell, tissue and organ cultures, evaluating the effects of compounds, observation, and adding physical and electrical stimuli. Therefore, the materials used to construct Microfluidic devices shall be selected with the Context of Use of the intended device functions.

The Context of Use of the end-user is not clarified at the time of device manufacture in some cases. In such cases, the Context of Use should still be determined when the device is designed. If determined in the design process, the Context of Use shall be documented.

b. processability

Processability is an indicator particularly needed for users developing microfluidics devices. PDMS is a typical example of a resin that is easy for users to process. The main chain of PDMS, formed by silicon and oxygen, is flexible due to its low internal molecular rotation energy and the mobility of the bond angles, while the methyl groups in the side chains result in low intermolecular interactions. As a result, it is one of the most flexible thermosetting resins and is used in soft lithography due to its high mould transferability. Unlike thermoplastics, the low-viscosity uncured material can be poured at room temperature into a convex moulding mould for forming flow channels, and no pressure is required on the moulding mould as in injection moulding or press moulding. This is particularly advantageous for the formation of microstructures and is suitable for moulding in moulding dies made by etching silicon wafers. The curing temperature is easy to control and can be cured at room temperature or by UV light irradiation, reducing the risk of bubble generation due to heating and the deviation between the moulding die's cross-sectional shape and the flow path's cross-sectional shape due to thermal shrinkage. No special equipment is required for pouring and curing the material, making it suitable for laboratory prototyping.

Processability is difficult to evaluate regarding numerical indicators, and it is expressed in writing.

c. Processing accuracy

A resin substrate with flow channels can be obtained by injection moulding or press moulding methods using a mould in which convex portions for forming flow channels are formed. When the mould is sufficiently filled with resin that has high processing accuracy, the deviation between the cross-sectional shape of the mould and the cross-sectional shape of the channels in the substrate is small, and the degree of deviation can be used as an indicator of the ease of processing of the resin material.

d. Autofluorescence

Autofluorescence is the fluorescence detected in plastic and resin materials when they are exposed to excitation light in the UV region. It is generally not a problem when observed under visible light. For example, when microfluidics is used for MPS, however, cells, tissues and organs cultured and maintained in the microfluidics can be fluorescently labelled and observed under a fluorescence microscope. In such cases, if the resin has autofluorescence, it becomes noise in the observed image and interferes with the observation. If the material has low autofluorescence, it is possible to prevent the observation from being disturbed by the emission of light from the material during observation.

In addition, when evaluating internal cells labelled with a fluorescent dye by fluorescence microscopy, the resin material's absorbance in the UV region of 100-400 nm, which corresponds to the excitation wavelength, must be low enough not to inhibit fluorescence excitation. Therefore, evaluating the spectrum of absorbance of the material is desirable.

e. Impact strength

Impact strength is a measure of the ability to withstand loads at high speeds without being destroyed. This indicator influences the density of the flow paths and other processes in the resin, as well as the fixing to culture apparatus or pipework form pumps and handling of the microfluidics substrate. It is an indicator that should be considered because if the strength is insufficient, the substrate can crack during channel processing. When the material with low impact strength is used, it will be difficult to fix the substrate strongly, or it may also hinder the formation of manifolds for tubing.

f. Transparency

Transparency is a key indicator for the observation of the contents of microfluidics. Not only for observing cells and tissues (ISO/FDIS 24479) when used as MPS but also for real-time monitoring of the microfluidics performance, for example, the mixing of liquids of different densities using the Schlieren phenomenon. The monitoring by microscopy is a matter of control for the entire microfluidics application and should be considered.

The transparency of the material itself is assessed by the transmittance of the material, i.e. the ratio of the total transmitted light flux to the parallel incident light flux.

g. Oxygen permeability

Oxygen permeability plays a major role in controlling oxygen concentrations when culturing and maintaining tissues, cells and organs in the device. For example, culture plates manufactured using highly oxygen-permeable resins have been shown to efficiently supply cells with oxygen from the bottom of the culture vessel and maintain liver function for a longer period of time than conventional resins using primary rat hepatocytes.[zz]

h. Adsorption and absorption

Adsorption and absorption are the uptake of substances by the device onto the material of the channel surface or other portion of the device, affecting the concentration of substances passing through the channel. Adsorption and absorption interfere with metrological measurements with microfluidics, and it is significant to evaluate adsorption and sorption on the object material to obtain reliable results in advance of the measurement.

i. Refractive index

When microfluidics is used for microscopic applications, the structure of microfluidics should be designed to suit the observation. Depending on the internal structure of the microfluidics and the difference in refractive index with water and solvents, the refractive index of the material largely affects the observation of the device using a microscope. It also affects the optics of normal microscopic observation. Therefore, the materials used in microfluidics, especially in the field of view, should have a refractive index suitable for the purpose of microscopic observation.

For example, when designing an objective lens, a cover glass with a thickness of 0.17 mm and a refractive index of 1.5 is a prerequisite, and the lens is designed to have the lowest aberration under these conditions. The value of the refractive index is also used to compensate for the difference between the distance travelled by the Z-stage (or objective lens) and the distance the focus of light is actually moved by it in the sample.

j. Biocompatibility

When microfluidics is used to retain cells inside for a long period of time, such as MPS, and to evaluate biological activities, the biocompatibility of the materials used in microfluidics is an important indicator. Some materials can be toxic and have a negative effect on cells, so materials that have not been certified to be biocompatible shall be evaluated for biocompatibility before use in microfluidics, where they come into contact with cells and tissues.

k. Sterilization resistance

The resistance, namely low dimensional change and transparency change, required to apply the sterilisation method appropriate for the material and end product application is significant indicator of the material used.

Sterilisation methods applied include but are not limited to, gamma sterilisation (ISO 11137-1 to 4), electron beam sterilisation, EOG sterilisation (ISO 11135), autoclave (ISO 17665), UV sterilisation and ethanol sterilisation. Of these sterilisation methods, gamma sterilisation, electron beam sterilisation and EOG sterilisation are most often employed by manufacturers of microfluidic producers. The typical user-side sterilisation method is autoclaving, which has the highest load on the material and therefore be evaluated for resistance to autoclave sterilisation.

When steam high-pressure sterilisation is applied, the resistance is the degree of dimensional change and reduction in permeability after steam sterilisation by autoclave. This indicator influences the applicability of steam sterilisation to the device.

III. Abbreviated terms

COC	Cyclic olefin copolymer
COP	cyclo olefin polymer
PC	polycarbonate
PDMS	polydimethylpolysiloxane
PMMA	methacrylic acid methyl ester
PMP	polymethylpentene
PP	polypropylene
PS	polystyrene
PV	polyvinyl
PVC	polyvinyl chloride

IV. Evaluation method

a. General

The indicators described in this document shall be measured by the method described in this clause. If indicators not shown in this document are essential for evaluating the material, the measurement method of those indicators shall be documented in detail. Where a consensus method of measurement is already available, it is recommended that this should be the preferred method of choice.

b. Processability

The processability is evaluated from the viewpoint of how easy it is to process the microfluidic device having channels for producing microfluidics. It shall be evaluated from the perspective of the user creating the microfluidics, such as whether special equipment is required, whether a mould is needed, whether it can be used in a 3D laser printer, etc. As a purposive evaluation is needed, what equipment and procedures will be required for manufacturing should be evaluated, especially after identifying the material and the intended use.

c. Processing accuracy

Processing accuracy is obtained by comparing the cross-sectional shape of the substrate and the mould after moulding. For example, using a scanning electron microscope or similar, an image of the cross-sectional shape of the substrate after moulding is obtained and compared with the cross-sectional shape of the mould. If the moulding accuracy of the mould is known to be sufficiently high compared to the design, the design shape can be changed to the cross-sectional shape of the actual mould. The processing accuracy is calculated by the transfer ratio. The transfer rate T (%) is calculated from the following formula:

$$T(\%) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{h_i}{H} \times 100$$

In the formula, h is the depth of the substrate after moulding, and H is the height of the moulding die or design shape. In addition, n indicates the number of the measurement. The transfer rate

can also be evaluated by the angle of the pattern of the forming mould or design shape and the angle of the substrate after forming, the cross-sectional area of the forming mould or design shape and the cross-sectional area of the substrate after forming, or a combination thereof. (See Annex a)

d. Autofluorescence

The autofluorescence index is the fluorescence intensity obtained using a fluorescence spectrophotometer calibrated with a constant light source. It is obtained by acquiring the fluorescence intensities of target samples processed in a given geometry and comparing them relative to each other.

Using a fluorescence spectrophotometer, the absorbance of the material in the UV region between 100 and 400 nm and the intensity of fluorescence in the visible light region can be compared relative to each other, and a material with relatively low intensity is determined to have low autofluorescence index. The measured values shall not be compared with known values, and all values to be compared must be taken at the same time.

The index is the relative autofluorescence intensity when the glass is set to 1.

e. Impact strength

Impact strength can be assessed according to the Charpy impact test [1] or the Izod impact test [2]. Specimens machined from specimen type A as described in reference [4] should be tested by notched edgewise impact. The units are kJ/mm².

When it is determined whether the strength after micro-processing is fit for the intended use, the strength after processing to that geometry should be measured. In cases where no specific geometry has been determined, and the material is to be processed by the customer, it should process the material to the standard geometry [9] (e.g. Fig. 2) and measure the strength. The sample geometry used for impact strength measurements shall be reported.

For materials that are too flexible or too thin, or soft materials such as rubber including PDMS, the tensile impact test [5] can be used, as the impact test is too strong to employ the Izod or Charpy impact test.

f. Transparency

Transmittance can be assessed by internationally standardised methods, e.g. the single-beam method [8]. Specimens can be cut from film, plate or injection or compression-moulded products, but should not exceed 10 mm in thickness and should be prepared in basically the same way as for devices. For example, if the device is injection-moulded, the specimen should be injection-moulded; if the device is machinable, the specimen should be machined. However, the specimen should be free from defects such as scratches, bubbles, etc., and free from adhesion of dust, grease, etc. The specimens should be large enough to cover the entrance opening of the integrating sphere, and there should be three specimens if there is no particular reason.

The measurements shall be state-conditioned at a temperature of $23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $(50 \pm 5)\%$ before the standard described test [3]. Time for condition adjustment shall be allowed for the specimen to reach thermal equilibrium. The measurements shall be carried out at a temperature of $23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $50 \pm 5\%$. In this case, the measurements shall be carried out after the equipment has been in operation long enough for thermal equilibrium to be reached.

The measuring device comprises a stabilised light source, an optical system combined with it and a photometer and an integrating sphere with an aperture. The integrating sphere should be kept free from external light flux. The ratio of the total light rays passed to the incident light specimen is determined as the transmittance, expressed in %.

A practical example of a measurement is shown in Annex.

As the bulk resin should not be used as it is for evaluation, the shape shall be identified and included in the report. For example, the shape of the Chip Topology [9] could be moulded with resin and the transparency could be evaluated using the central part.

The number of assessment measurements and the statistical treatment shall be reported.

g. Oxygen permeability

Oxygen permeability shall be evaluated on the basis of generally referenced standards such as international standards. It can be evaluated according to ISO 2782-1 (vulcanised and thermoplastic rubbers), ISO 15105-2 (plastics - films and sheets) or other standards such as ASTM D1434 [yy]. These standards are applicable to films, sheets, laminates, co-extrusions and flexible plastic-coated materials. The thickness of the specimen should not exceed 4 mm. The measuring principle is to measure the gas permeability by keeping a vacuum on one side (low pressure side) separated by the test piece and introducing the prescribed test gas on the other side (high pressure side), allowing the test gas to permeate the test piece by using the pressure difference as a driving force, and measuring the change over time in pressure on the low pressure side due to gas permeation. The measurable temperature range is 10 to 80 °C and the temperature dependence of oxygen permeability can be measured. As the removal of carbon dioxide emitted during cell culture is also important, the carbon dioxide permeability of the material can also be measured in a similar way.

h. Adsorption and absorption

Drug adsorption and absorption properties shall be assessed by adding the target drug to a container, incubating it for a certain period of time, collecting the residual drug and measuring the amount of drug remaining. The drug residual can be measured by HPLC (UV, fluorescence, mass spectrometer, etc.), plate reader (UV, fluorescence), etc.

Proteins and nucleic acids (DNA, RNA) are among the drugs envisaged for use in the device, and residual amounts are measured using the methods described above and appropriate measurement techniques. (See Annex D).

i. refractive index

Refractive index measurement methods that are commonly used in solids shall be used. Standardised methods include the minimum declination (ISO 21395-1:2020) and the V-block (ISO 21395-2:2022). Each refractive index measurement method has its own characteristics, and the method should be selected according to the application of the material in the microfluidics device.

j. Biocompatibility

When using a new material of unknown biocompatibility, whose toxicity is not yet known, the toxicity of the material on cells shall be investigated. Known cytotoxicity tests [6] can be used as an evaluation method.

k. Sterilization resistance

When using cells, such as MPS, the materials used in microfluidics shall be resistant to the sterilisation methods applied. Resistance is the degree of dimensional change and minimal change in transparency due to sterilisation treatment.

The resistance required when applying steam sterilisation is checked using moulded products made from various resins. Steam sterilisation is performed [7] and dimensional changes, including deformation and shrinkage, are visually checked before and after implementation. If a device is ready for actual use, steam sterilise the device and check the dimensional changes. At that time, if necessary, changes in the microstructure of the flow channel and other parts can be checked using SEM, etc.

Similarly, after steam sterilisation, transparency is checked by the change in transmittance before and after sterilisation. Transmittance measurements can be carried out following the method described in chapter 6.5. As with dimensional changes, if a device is available, it should be used to assess the change. However, the device shall be of a measurable size, such that it can be accommodated in a spectrophotometer and cover the aperture of the integrating sphere without leakage.

V. Reperentaion of material properties

The properties of the materials comprising the microfluidics device that are used as reference for material selection are expressed in a matrix of indices based on measurements and evaluations of the indices that are relevant to the intended use.

VI. Report

The items evaluated for the selection of the materials used for the microfluidics device, including ease of processing, fluorescence properties, impact strength, transparency, oxygen permeability, absorption, adsorption, refractive index, toxicity and sterilisation resistance, shall be reported. The indexes relevant to the intended use shall include, but not limited to, the following:

- A) the results of the evaluation of easy processing,
- B) transfer rate, the result of processing accuracy evaluation,
- C) relative fluorescence intensity for the evaluation of autofluorescence properties,
- D) impact strength and the resin shape used for its measurement,
- E) transparency and the resin shape used for its evaluation,
- F) oxygen permeability and the resin geometry used to its measure,
- G) absorption and adsorption coefficient and the resin geometry used for its evaluation,
- H) refractive index and resin geometry used for its evaluation,
- I) results of toxicity tests when new materials are used for the device,
- J) applicable sterilisation methods,
- K) dimensional and transparency changes after the sterilisation resistance assessment,
- L) number of measurements and statistical treatment for each test evaluated, and

- indicators not shown in this document and their specific measurement methods.

VII. Annex (informative)

a. An example of evaluation method of processing accuracy

a-1. Principle of the measurement methods

Processing accuracy is evaluated as the shape of the channels fabricated on the substrate has a small deviation from the shape of the forming mould and sufficient forming transfer is obtained. The shape of the channels fabricated on the substrate using the forming mould is measured using an image analyser to measure the height, angle and cross-sectional area of the mould and the cross-sectional area of the flow path, and the ratio of the height, angle and cross-sectional area of the flow path to the set values for the mould height, angle and cross-sectional area is determined. The closer the ratio is to 1, the more sufficient forming transfer has been obtained, the closer the ratio is to 1, the more adequate the moulding transfer is.

Key

1. Mold
2. Mold cross-sectional area
3. Mold angle
4. Mold height
5. Flow channel
6. Flow channel cross-sectional area
7. Flow channel angle
8. Flow channel height

Fig A.1 Evaluation method of processing accuracy

b. An example of evaluation method of autofluorescence

b-1. Principle of the measurement methods

Autofluorescence from materials is measured with a spectrophotometer calibrated at a constant light source. Specimens can be cut from film, plate or injection- or compression-moulded products, but should not exceed 10 mm in thickness and should be prepared in the same way as for devices. For example, if the device is injection moulded, the specimen should be injection moulded; if the device is machinable, the specimen should be machined. However, the specimen shall be free from defects such as scratches, bubbles, etc., and shall be free from dust, grease, etc., and shall be large enough to cover the entrance aperture.

Specimens that have been prepared for a long time shall not be used for measurements, as fluorescent properties can easily be altered by UV light and oxidative degradation.

Autofluorescence should be measurements at a temperature of $23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $50 \pm 5\%$. The excitation and detection wavelengths at the time of measurement are determined according to the intended use of the device. For example, if the sample (cell) used in the device is to be observed at an excitation wavelength of 495 nm and a detection wavelength of 525 nm, the measurement should be carried out under the same conditions at 495 nm and 525 nm respectively.

Autofluorescence of all materials to be compared shall be measured at the same time and the fluorescence properties determined by relative comparison of the detected values. In the case of additional comparisons, the newly measured values shall not be compared with the known measured values, but the autofluorescence of all materials to be compared shall be measured again.

c. An example of evaluation method of permeability

c-1. Principle of the measurement methods

Oxygen permeability is measured from gas permeability equipment, and carbon dioxide can be measured with the same equipment. Test specimens can be films, sheets, laminates, co-extrusions and flexible plastic-coated materials. The thickness should not exceed 4 mm. Generally, the differential pressure gas permeability measurement method is used. A specimen of a certain thickness is used, the oxygen transmission is measured, and the oxygen transmission coefficient is the value obtained by dividing the oxygen transmission coefficient by the thickness of the specimen.

Gas permeability is temperature dependent, and tests shall be carried out under the specified temperature (generally 23°C) and at 0% humidity.

For comparing the measured values, materials to be compared shall be measured under the same conditions.

Measurement samples are prepared, for example, by cutting test pieces of several tens of micrometres to 4 mm thick into 90 x 90 mm pieces, the diameter of the measurement section depending on the measurement device. If the oxygen permeability is high depending on the test piece, an aluminium mask is applied to the sample beforehand to reduce the actual permeable area for measurement. Samples that have been subjected to microfabrication, surface modification, etc. can also be measured.

d. An example of evaluation method of permeability

d-1. An example of drug measurement method

Drug adsorption and absorption properties are evaluated by measuring the amount of drug remaining after adsorption and absorption of the added target drug. The added drug can be adjusted using phosphate buffer solution (PBS). After adding the target drug to the container, incubate at a fixed temperature and period (e.g. 24 or 48 hours), collect the residual drug and measure the residual amount. The amount adsorbed or absorbed is calculated from the amount added and the amount remaining.

Residual drug can be measured by HPLC (e.g. UV, fluorescence, mass spectrometer), plate reader (UV, fluorescence).

The materials to be compared should be measured under the same condition and the measured values are compared. For example, the materials to be compared should have a similar shape, especially if they have the same surface area in contact with the drug.

d-2. An example of method for protein adsorption and absorption measurement

Protein absorption and adsorption are measured using storage containers made from various materials. The container, such as a syringe, tube or vial, is sealed with the protein solution and allowed to come into contact with the container for a predetermined time, after which it is collected. and the initial and post-collection concentrations are compared. If a decrease in concentration is observed after collection, it can be confirmed that adsorption and absorption to the container has occurred. To calculate the specific amount of adsorption, the solution concentration, the contact area of the various containers and the contact time are used to convert the amount of adsorption per unit area and time.

If it is possible to prepare the device for actual use, it can also be used for evaluation. The device is passed through a solution containing protein and then collected, and the presence or absence of absorption and adsorption is assessed by checking the difference in protein concentration between the initial and post-fluidisation periods.

Phosphate buffer solution (PBS) or similar solutions can be used to prepare the protein solution, but it is preferable to use buffer solutions designed for actual use.

HPLC (UV detector, fluorescence detector, mass spectrometer), UV detection with a plate reader, fluorescence detection, etc. can be used to confirm concentration differences.

d-3. An example of method for nucleic acids adsorption and absorption measurement

The adsorption of nucleic acids can be measured by the same method. TE buffer, EDTA solution, SSC buffer, DNase/RNase-free ultrapure water, etc. can be used to prepare solutions, but it is preferable to use solutions designed for actual use. The detection method should be selected in consideration of the type and concentration of the evaluation sample.

e. An example of evaluation method of total light transmittance

e-1. An example of drug measurement of light transmittance

The transmittance shall be evaluated by Single-beam instrument [8].

In advance to the measurement, cut out three test pieces on a flat plate, such as a film or plate not exceeding 10 mm in thickness, large enough to cover the entry opening of the integrating sphere,

and check that they are free from scratches, bubbles and other defects, as well as from dust, grease and other contaminants.

The measurements are conditioned at a temperature of $23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $50 \pm 5\%$ in accordance with the Standard atmospheres for conditioning and testing reference [3] Prior to the testing, wait until the specimens reach thermal equilibrium. The equipment shall also be conditioned at a temperature of $23^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a relative humidity of $50 \pm 5\%$, allowing sufficient time for thermal equilibrium to be reached after the equipment has been in operation.

When measuring, set the test specimen with care so that no external light flux enters the integrating sphere.

As it is not possible to use the bulk resin as it is for evaluation, the shape is identified, and this information is included in the report. For example, the shape of the Chip Topology [9] could be moulded with resin and its central part could be used to evaluate transparency.

The number and statistical treatment of the evaluation measurements and the spectra at each wavelength are recorded and reported.

f. An example of steam sterilization resistance

f-1. An example of drug measurement of light transmittance

Steam sterilisation resistance is evaluated using moulded products made from various resins; steam sterilisation is evaluated according to the Sterilisation of health care products standard [7] and the dimensional changes before and after the sterilisation are visually checked, including deformation and shrinkage. Prepare plate-shaped moulded products and check their dimensions after steam sterilisation. Visually check the moulded products for obvious changes, including distortion and shrinkage, and judge resins with small changes to be highly resistant to steam sterilisation. The sterilisation resistance is reported by description of the visual observation.

Transparency is evaluated by checking the change in transmittance before and after steam sterilisation using the method described in chapter 6.5. The spectrophotometer results of the moulded product are compared before and after steam sterilisation and the resin with the smallest change is judged to have high resistance to steam sterilisation.

Bibliography

- [1] ISO 179-1, *Plastics — Determination of Charpy impact properties — Part 1: Non-instrumented impact test*
- [2] ISO 180, *Plastics — Determination of Izod impact strength*
- [3] ISO 291, *Plastics — Standard atmospheres for conditioning and testing*
- [4] ISO 3167, *Plastics — Multipurpose test specimens*
- [5] ISO 8256, *Plastics — Determination of tensile-impact strength*
- [6] ISO 10993-5, *Biological evaluation of medical devices — Part 5: Tests for in vitro cytotoxicity*
- [7] ISO 11140-1, *Sterilization of health care products — Chemical indicators — Part 1: General requirements*
- [8] ISO 13468-1, *Plastics — Determination of the total luminous transmittance of transparent materials — Part 1: Single-beam instrument*
- [9] ISO 22916, *Microfluidic devices — Interoperability requirements for dimensions, connections and initial device classification*
- [yy] ASTM D1434, *Standard Test Method for Determining Gas Permeability Characteristics of Plastic Film and Sheeting*
- [zz] Nishikawa M, Ito H, Tokito F, Hirono K, Inamura K, Scheidecker B, Danoy M, Kawanishi T, Arakawa H, Kato Y, Esashika K, Miyasako H, Sakai Y. Accurate Evaluation of Hepatocyte Metabolisms on a Noble Oxygen-Permeable Material With Low Sorption Characteristics. *Front Toxicol.* 2022 Jun 6;4:810478. doi: 10.3389/ftox.2022.810478. PMID: 35733832; PMCID: PMC9208656.